

EVALUATION OF INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH AND MODE I/II FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF CURVED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The investigation of the interlaminar shear strength and the fracture toughness in mode I and II loading are useful for evaluating the consolidation quality of samples produced by the filament winding technology.

A method for measuring the shear strength of thin curved samples is proposed herein. Stress distribution within the probe is calculated and evaluated by finite element method.

The curved double cantilever beam (CDCB) test is a method to measure mode I delamination toughness of curved composite materials. A finite element model for this geometry is presented, that takes into consideration nonlinear deformational effects, orthotropic material properties and local mixed mode load at crack-tip.

INTRODUCTION

A very promising processing method for thermoplastic fibre reinforced composites is the filament winding technology that manufactures ring structures. The characterization of the delamination properties is a very important task for testing of composite materials. The interlaminar shear strength and the fracture toughness in mode I or II loading are the most sensitive quantities for evaluating the fabrication quality especially the consolidation of the composite rings.

There are few experimental possibilities for interlaminar shear testing in comparison to inplane shear testing. The usually applied method in shear strength measurement is the short-beam test, however, with thermoplastics it is difficult to meet the requirements of the standard and it has been proved that the failure mode during three point bending of multi-ply specimens is rather complex (see Whitney [1]). Other test set-ups are single and double lap joint tests. A literature survey and discussions of the benefits and draw-backs of these tests is given, for example, by Kinloch [2] and Tarnopolskii [3]. However, all these tests are for plane samples only and that is the reason why we have developed a method for measuring the interlaminar shear strength of curved samples. Some experimental results concerning filament wound ring samples have been published in [4].

A standard test for characterizing mode I delamination toughness of straight laminate samples is the Double-Cantilever Beam (DCB)-Specimen. As an equivalent test method for curved structures produced by the filament winding technology the Curved Double Cantilever Beam (CDCB) geometry has been proposed in the literature (Foral [5]; Wittich [6]; Lauke, Friedrich [7]). Though very similar designed to DCB-test no analytical model has been developed to

describe the deformational behaviour of the CDCB-specimen. The problems originate from its curved geometry, that complicates elasto-mechanic differential equations, introduces an unsymmetric loading resulting in a mixed mode crack-tip loading state and- due to rotation and large deflection effects- enhances nonlinearity of the deformational behaviour.

Owing to this difficulties only some coarse schemes for reduction of experimental datas of the CDCB-test has been reported in literature ([6], [7]), relying on very general approximations (Compliance Method, method after Williams [8]). Though they allow an interpretation of test results in quality, some improvements in quantity will be expected by a more sophisticated analysis. For this purpose a finite element (FE) model of the CDCB-test has been developed, that overcomes the above mentioned problems. It provides the basis for analysis of experimental results and can be used as a measure for approximate analytic models.

SHEAR STRENGTH AND STRESS DISTRIBUTION

After the application of the filament winding technique rings of unidirectional (circumferentially) reinforced composites are obtained with the diameter of the mandrel.

The rings are prepared for testing by grinding and cutting them (with a diamond saw) into quarter pieces. These samples with an arc length L , width B and thickness D are now tested under compression load to obtain the interlaminar shear strength. The loading system is shown in Figure 1, however for a sample without a foil as a starter crack. More details of the test-set-up are explained in [9].

Figure 1. Experimental test-set-up for curved composite samples for shear strength and mode II fracture toughness measurements

The applied force acts in a certain angle Θ to the fracture plane. The component F in this direction can easily be obtained by the balance of forces and moments acting at the whole element (see [4]). From the force measurement the shear strength is obtained by

$$\tau_f = \tau_{\max} = F_{\max}/A_0 \tag{1}$$

with $A_0 = B \times L$ as the sample area within which the force acts. The tests have shown that delamination starts in the even moment when the maximum load is reached.

A shear strength criterion is based on the inherent assumption that the sample fails simultaneously at all points within the delamination area. This would require a homogeneous stress distribution and a sample without defects. The latter will never be the case in practice, however, the former

one depends on the test conditions and material properties. To examine the stress situation in the sample a FE-model has been established. As material properties the values $E_{\theta} = 35$ GPa, $E_r = 5$ GPa, $G_{\theta r} = 2.5$ GPa, $\nu_{\theta r} = 0.3$, typical for unidirectionally reinforced glass-fibre polyamide, have been used.

The commercial finite element software ANSYS was applied for the analysis. The investigated geometry, shown in Fig. 1, was modelled by a 2D-analysis with 4-node isoparametric elements. The following boundary conditions have been used for the analysis: $u_r(r=0, r=D) = 0$, $u_{\theta}(\theta=0, D/2 \leq r \leq D) = 0$, $\sigma_{\theta}(\theta=\Theta, 0 \leq r \leq D/2) = \sigma_0$, i.e. they are non-symmetric to examine the influence of constant load (at the upper bound) and constant displacement (at the lower bound). To determine the influence of the aspect ratio L/D of the specimen three different FE-models were calculated: $L = 4.58$ mm ($\theta = 5$ deg), $L = 9.16$ mm ($\theta = 10$ deg), and $L = 18.32$ mm ($\theta = 20$ deg). The stresses are normalized by the nominal shear stress according to eqn. 1 ($\tau_0 = F/A_0$) to provide the stress concentrations:

$$k_{r\theta} = \sigma_{r\theta}/\tau_0 \quad k_{rr} = \sigma_{rr}/\tau_0 \quad k_{\theta\theta} = \sigma_{\theta\theta}/\tau_0 \quad (2)$$

Figure 2 shows the effect of varying aspect ratios on the shear stress concentration along the sample arc length, l , for the centre line $r=D/2$.

Figure 2. Shear stress concentration along the sample arc length for different aspect ratios, $D=5$ mm, $r = D/2$

The examination of these data shows that the stress concentration is highest for the longest sample in the end regions. (The distribution is non-symmetrical because of the different boundary conditions on both sides). For $L/D \approx 2$ the stress distributions is rather uniform in the centre of the sample. It becomes clear that there exists an optimum aspect ratio which depends additionally on the material properties used. For the evaluation of the stress situation it is also necessary to consider the normal stress concentrations. As Figure 3 shows the normal stresses σ_{rr} are rather low in comparison to the shear stress except in the end regions, and they are compressive in nature, preventing mode I failure (the constant displacement boundary condition at $\theta=0$ is more appropriate than that of $\sigma_{\theta} = \text{const.}$ at $\theta=\Theta$). Analogue results have been obtained for $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$.

Figure 3. Normal stress concentration along the sample arc length for different aspect ratios, $D=5\text{mm}$, $r=D/2$

Although the shear stress distribution along the curved compression shear sample is not uniform in general an optimum aspect ratio (dependent on the material properties) can be found where the test set-up is appropriate to determine the interlaminar shear strength of composites. In further work it is intended to examine the mode II fracture toughness of such samples.

FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF CURVED SAMPLES

The CDCB-Specimen consists of a composite material quarter ring with fibers oriented in circumferential direction, an artificial crack notch of length a_0 introduced in the thickness-midplane during processing by means of a PI-foil and two pierced aluminium loading blocks glued at the cantilever ends (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Geometry of the CDCB-model

During experiment the loading force-displacement dependence $P(\delta)$ for stable crack-extension is monitored together with debonding crack length a .

The FE-model is built up from 8-node 2D-solid elements with orthotropic linear elastic material properties and utilizes nonlinear analysis in order to account for large deflection and rotational effects. A highly refined crack-tip region makes possible the direct evaluation of mixed-mode stress intensity factors K_I and K_{II} from singular stress fields. The crack tip is formed by a ring of quarter-node point crack-tip elements which size can be chosen as small as 1/5000 of specimen thickness H . Since the FE-model is fully parameterized, it easily allows variation of geometric and material properties.

The debonding toughness is characterized by a critical value for the energy release rate G_c , that is defined by the change in total potential energy with crack length. It can be computed (for constant loading displacement δ) by:

$$G(a, \delta) = -\frac{1}{B} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial U_{el}}{\partial a} \right)_{\delta=\text{const}} \quad (3)$$

from the change in elastic stored energy U_{el} , that can be directly obtained from the FE-program as the elements strain energy.

An alternative to compute $G(a, \delta)$ from the (nonlinear) loading force-displacement dependence $P(a, \delta)$:

$$G(a, \delta) = -\frac{1}{B} \int_0^{\delta(a)} d\delta' \left[\frac{dP(a, \delta')}{da} \right] \quad (4),$$

proved to provide the same results for our FE-model. For this analysis computation after equ. 3 was preferred, economizing the integration process that would be necessary for equ. 4.

The function $U_{el}(a, \delta)$ was interpolated from the FE-model results for elastic strain energy $U_{el}(a_i, \delta_j)$ at discrete crack lengths a_i and loading displacements δ_j .

To characterize the mixed mode state the stress intensity factors K_I and K_{II} were extrapolated to $r \rightarrow 0$ from the relative displacements of adjacent crack-face points in the vicinity of the FE-models crack-tip:

$$u_y^{\text{upper crack face}}(r) - u_y^{\text{lower crack face}}(r) = -2 \cdot K_I \sqrt{\frac{2r}{\pi}} \cdot \text{Im} \left[a_{22} \cdot \frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{\mu_1 \mu_2} \right] \quad (5a)$$

$$u_x^{\text{upper crack face}}(r) - u_x^{\text{lower crack face}}(r) = 2 \cdot K_{II} \sqrt{\frac{2r}{\pi}} \cdot \text{Im} [a_{11} \cdot (\mu_1 + \mu_2)] \quad (5b)$$

These equations correspond to the singular terms at a crack-tip in orthotropic elastic materials (Sih, Paris, Irwin [10]) in the local coordinate system with origin at the moving crack tip. The energy release rate $G(a, \delta)$ is related to the results for K_I and K_{II} by:

$$G(a, \delta) = -\frac{K_I}{2E_y} \cdot \text{Im} \left(\frac{K_I \cdot (\mu_1 + \mu_2) + K_{II}}{\mu_1 \cdot \mu_2} \right) + \frac{K_{II}}{2E_x} \cdot \text{Im} (K_{II} \cdot (\mu_1 + \mu_2) + K_I \cdot \mu_1 \cdot \mu_2) \quad (6)$$

where m_1, m_2 are complex and a_{11}, a_{22} real constants, derived from anisotropic elastic properties.

The FE-results for energy release rate $G(a, \delta)$ after equ. 3 are displayed in Fig. 5 for a specimen with representative geometric and material properties (elastic moduli: $E_x=50\text{GPa}$, $E_y=E_z=5\text{GPa}$, $G_{xz}=2.5\text{GPa}$, ring geometry: $r_i=50\text{mm}$, thickness $H=5\text{mm}$, block length $l_k=20\text{mm}$, $h_{kl}=9\text{mm}$).

Figure 5. Contour plot of energy release rate $G\left(a, \frac{\delta}{a}\right)$ versus crack length a and normalized loading displacement $\frac{\delta}{a}$.

For short crack lengths a there is an extremely sharp increase of energy release rate $G(a, \delta)$ with normalized loading displacement δ/a .

Thermoplastic composite materials have a critical debonding energy release rate of about $G_c = 1.. 2 \text{ kJ/m}^2$. Considering short crack lengths, this rate is exceeded even for very small deflections $(\delta/a) \leq 0.1$, justifying linear analysis for this case. But with increasing crack length, a , the critical displacement for crack-extension δ_c grows (nearly linearly) into the large deflection/nonlinear deformation range. The consequences for neglect of nonlinear deformation are given in Ref. [11]

A main purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of the mode II contribution to the fracture toughness originating from the unsymmetrical geometry of the CDCB-sample. On the basis of equ. 5 the stress intensity factors K_I and K_{II} were calculated. The determined ratio K_{II}/K_I could be shown to be independent of the crack length and deformation δ .

The investigation of the mixed mode state revealed, that in general the mode II part of the crack-tip loading is smaller than 5-10% of the K_I value. This justifies the identification of the measured critical energy-release rate with the pure mode I value G_c .

The model will be used in future to investigate the influence of anisotropic material properties (in analogy to [12]), to discuss optimum specimen design and to examine the applicability of a simple analytic beam theory model for analysis of CDCB-test results.

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